

SOME CANADIAN LUNAR SCIENCE INSTRUMENTS. K. A. Carroll, Canadensys Aerospace Corporation, Bolton, Ontario, Canada (kieran.carroll@canadensys.com).

Introduction: Canadensys has developed instruments that have landed and operated on the lunar surface, and has several other instruments in development, including several for flight programs that are scheduled to fly to the lunar surface within the next 2-3 years. Versions of these instruments may be relevant to upcoming European lunar surface missions, for example the Argonaut lunar lander, and the Lunar Prospecting and Scouting Rover (LPSR). In this talk we describe these instruments, and the missions that that have flown in/will fly on.

Figure 2. NISA Camera (186 deg fisheye lens shown).

NISA Cameras: The Nano Immersive Situational Awareness (NISA) space camera is a compact (50x50x39 mm), low-mass (0.135 kg with fisheye lens) instrument which uses a 3000x4000 pixel CMOS detector array (both B&W and colour versions available), and can be equipped with a variety of lens options. 17 NISAs have been flown on 3 lunar lander missions to date (ispace’s Hakuto-R Mission 1, Intuitive Machines’ IM-1 “Odysseus”, and IM-2 “Athena”). While these cameras were not manifested on these missions as science instruments *per se*, images from some of those cameras were taken which are of scientific interest, as well as being very significant in terms of helping to diagnose mission

Figure 4. Image of IM-1 Odysseus when landing on the lunar surface.

Figure 1. NISA image of IM-2 Athena lander on the lunar surface.

anomalies (Figures 2, 3). Many additional NISA cameras are manifested on other upcoming lunar lander and rover missions.

RMM: The Rover Multispectral Microscope is a science instrument based on the NISA camera. It is an active multispectral imager, using a set of 5 narrow-bandwidth LEDs (with wavelengths ranging from 365 to 940 nm) to illuminate nearby targets, and a 12 mm f/4 lens focused at a nominal distance of 20 cm. It is one instrument in the Lunar Vertex instrument suite (funded by NASA under the PRISM program), developed by JHU/APL to explore the Reiner Gamma lunar swirl feature; RMM is mounted aboard a small lunar rover which will characterize the texture and composition of the regolith as the rover traverses the swirl. P.I. David Blewett will use data from all the Lunar Vertex instruments to test various theories regarding the origin of Reiner Gamma’s mysterious swirl feature. This mission is currently expected to fly in 2026, carried to the Moon aboard Intuitive Machines’ IM-3 lander (the flight arranged via NASA’s CLPS program).

Figure 3. RMM Flight Model in cleanroom.

MSI & MSI-1000: Two additional second-generation Multispectral Imagers are currently under development, incorporating advancements based on lessons learned in developing RMM. These are planned to fly aboard the Lunar Rover Mission (LRM) that Canadensys is currently developing for the Canadian Space Agency; this ~ 40 kg rover, which will be carried to the Moon aboard a CLPS lander after 2027, is a joint CSA/NASA mission, which carries several other Canadian and US instruments in addition to the two MSIs. One of the MSIs will cover a spectral range similar to that of RMM, while the other (MSI-1000) will have at least one LED wavelength longer than 1000 nm. Unlike RMM, the MSI's are mounted to the front face of the LRM rover, looking somewhat forward, and hence are designed to have a longer nominal in-focus distance (~ 1 m), allowing larger rocks to be imaged in their entirety.

LHANS: The LRM rover will also carry the Lunar Hydrogen Autonomous Neutron Spectrometer instrument, developed by Bubble Technologies Inc. This instrument has a mass of 1.4 kg, a volume of 14x20x10 cm, and power consumption of 5 W. It comprises a neutron spectrometer and a gamma-ray spectrometer, detecting albedo neutrons and gamma rays produced in the upper 1 m of the lunar surface by cosmic radiation particle impacts, to detect the signatures of several atomic species (H mainly via neutron spectroscopy; Ti, Fe, Ca, P, K, Th, and U mainly using gamma-ray spectroscopy). This can be used to detect deposits of water ice, and also help constrain local rock mineralogy.

Figure 6. LRM LHANS prototype instrument.

Figure 5: VEGA TRL-5 prototype in thermal-vacuum test chamber

VEGA: The Vector Gravimeter/Accelerometer (VEGA) instrument can be used on planetary surfaces as a gravimeter, and on free-flying spacecraft as an accelerometer. It is specifically designed to be used to carry out geophysical gravimetry surveys on the lunar surface, for the same purpose for which such surveys are carried out on Earth --- in order to detect subsurface density anomalies, which can constrain theories regarding the local geology in the survey area, and thus explore for mineral resources and/or address scientific questions about the formation and structure of the subsurface rock layers. A TRL-5/6 design has been developed, with a mass of 2.1 kg, dimensions of 10x10x19 cm and a power consumption of 5-10 W; this has included performance testing in a thermal-vacuum chamber, which has demonstrated measurement repeatability of 2 ppm, compatible with achieving 0.3 mGal measurement accuracy on the lunar surface. VEGA is unusual in that it is an absolute vector gravimeter (unlike most geophysical instruments which are relative, and scalar); this makes it particularly suitable for use on small, slow-moving lunar rovers.